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ZIGBEE: A LOW POWER WIRELESS TECHNOLOGY FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT:

The great potential of Wireless Sensor Network is being seen in industrial, consumer and commercial application. The wireless technology is becoming one of the most prominent areas of research. This paper focuses on the most widely used transceiver standard in Wireless Sensor Networks, a ZigBee technology. ZigBee over IEEE 802.15.4 defines specifications for low data rate WPAN (LR-WPAN) to support low power monitoring and controlling devices. This paper presents a Zigbee wireless standard, IEEE 802.15.4specification, ZigBee device types, the protocol stack architecture and its applications.

KEYWORDS:

ZigBee, IEEE802.15.4

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DYNAMIC MODELLING AND OPTIMAL CONTROL SCHEME OF WHEEL INVERTED PENDULUM FOR MOBILE ROBOT APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Unstable wheel inverted pendulum is modelled and controlled deploying Kane's method and optimal partial-state PID control scheme. A correct derivation of nonlinear mathematical model of a wheel inverted pendulum is obtained using a proper definition of the geometric context of active and inertia forces. Then the model is decoupled to two linear subsystems namely balancing and heading subsystems. Afterward partial-state PID controller is proposed and formulated to quadratic optimal regulation tuning method. It enables partial-state PID to be optimally tuned and guarantees a satisfactory level of states error and a realistic utilization of torque energy. Simulation and numerical analyses are carried out to analyse system's stability and to determine the performance of the proposed controller for mobile wheel inverted pendulum application.

KEYWORDS

Wheel inverted pendulum, Kane's method, partial-state PID, quadratic optimal regulation tuning

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INTEGRAL BACKSTEPPING SLIDING MODE CONTROL OF CHAOTIC FORCED VAN DER POL OSCILLATOR

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ABSTRACT

Forced Van der Pol oscillator exhibits chaotic behaviour and instability under certain parameters and this poses a great threat to the systems where it has been applied hence, the need to develop a control method to stabilize and control chaos in a Forced Van der Pol oscillator so as to avoid damage in the controlled system and also to prevent unmodeled dynamics from being introduced in the system. Sliding Mode control makes use of the regulatory variables derived from the controlled Lyapunov function to bring the new variables to stability. The essence of using Integral Backstepping was to prevent chattering which can occur in the control input and can cause instability to the system by igniting unmodeled dynamics. Simulation was done using MATLAB and the results were provided to show the effectiveness of the proposed control method. Integral Backstepping Sliding Mode control method was effective towards stability and chaos control. It was also robust towards matched and unmatched disturbance.

KEYWORDS

Chaos Control, Lyapunov Function, Van der Pol Oscillator, Sliding Mode, Integral Backstepping

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TAKAGI-SUGENO MODEL FOR QUADROTOR MODELLING AND CONTROL USING NONLINEAR STATE FEEDBACK CONTROLLER

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a Takagi-Sugeno (T-S) model for Quadrotor modelling. This model is developed using multiple model approach, composed of three locally accurate models valid in different region of the operating space. It enables us to model the global nonlinear system with some degree of accuracy. Once the T-S model has been defined it is claimed to be relatively straightforward to design a controller with the same strategy of T-S model. A nonlinear state feedback controller based on Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI), and PDC technique with pole placement constraint is synthesized. The requirements of stability and poleplacement in LMI region are formulated based on the Lyapunov direct method. By recasting these constraints into LMIs, we formulate an LMI feasibility problem for the design of the nonlinear state feedback controller. This controller is applied to a nonlinear Quadrotor system, which is one of the most complex flying systems that exist. A comparative study between controller with stability constraints and controller with pole placement constrains is made. Simulation results show that the controller with pole placement constrains yields good tracking performance. The designed T-S model is validated using Matlab Simulink.

KEYWORDS

Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI), Multiple Model Approach (MMA), Parallel Disturbance Compensation (PDC), Pole Placement, Quadrotor, Takagi-Sugeno model.

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